

Methodological and Ideological Options

Doing more with less: Provisioning systems and the transformation of the stock-flow-service nexus

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ABSTRACT

Physical components of societies like infrastructures need biophysical resources for their construction, maintenance and use. These components, analyzed as societies' material stocks, predefine energy and raw materials and provide societal services, necessary for their functioning and for social welfare. The nexus between stocks, the resource flows and the services, is crucial for the analysis of social-ecological transformations. In this paper, we build on recent work in socio-metabolic research on the stock-flow-service nexus and develop a conceptual approach how to examine this nexus while addressing the challenges of social-ecological transformations. We refer to the concept of provisioning systems to analyze the institutions, technologies, knowledge and practices mediating between actors and resources but also the power relations involved in the creation and transformation of this nexus. It enables us to understand how specific stock-flow-service nexuses are constructed, which lock-in effects result from specific stock-flow-service configurations and which options can be envisaged for its transformation towards lower resource use. We argue that provisioning systems need to be analyzed as structuring space and time as well as embedded within the contested terrain of the state. By providing this conceptualization, we aim to offer an understanding which can help to define options for the transformation of the stock-flow-service nexus in a transdisciplinary process.

1. Introduction

Material stocks, for example infrastructures, buildings, machines or dams, are physical structures created through socially organized flows of materials, energy and human labor, produced and reproduced through social metabolism (Fischer-Kowalski and Weisz, 1999; Haberl et al., 2019). They are important components of societal development and create challenges, but also opportunities for transformations towards sustainability (Faber et al., 2005). First, they enable certain modes of development, e.g. concerning the mobility offered by railways or roads or the communication facilitated by IT infrastructures. Specific patterns and levels of stocks promote certain ways of living (e.g. patterns of urbanization) and production (e.g. just in time production), which have repercussions on further resource use. Secondly, material stocks determine the energy and materials required for its further use and for its maintenance or its disposal and thus have strong influence on the further

metabolism of societies (Ayres and Simonis, 1994; Fischer-Kowalski, 1998). For example, automotive transport requires construction materials (for building and maintenance of roads), energy (e.g. petrol), and technology (combustion or e-motors) to use and maintain these stocks. Third, once created material stocks represent challenges for alternative development paths. Due to the concrete specific patterns of stocks established in certain regions and the societal services they enable; further pathways of resource needs and thus lock-in effects are determined (Seto et al., 2016). To change an existing system of stocks is difficult for several reasons: Additional funding must be provided and material and additional energy flows are required. Social behavior or practices i.e. routinized forms of behavior, often exercised without explicit reflection or rational choices must be transformed and the vested interests and power relations involved in the former system are challenged and will probably oppose such transformations. Even though a transformation of a given system seems indispensable given current

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agreements on climate change mitigation (IPCC, 2018), and despite the fact that new technologies may emerge, motivated by socioeconomic interests, existing stocks represent major obstacles for alternative development paths. They create major challenges for the transformation towards a sustainable level of resource use.

At the global level, more than half of the annual resource extraction is currently used to build up, expand and maintain material stocks (Krausmann et al., 2017b). Although climate change mitigation measures and other sustainability actions to reach the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) require the reduction of global resource and energy levels, current levels and their impacts are still unsustainable (Akenji et al., 2016; IPBES, 2019; IRP, 2019; UNEP, 2016; Schandl et al., 2017; Krausmann et al., 2018). Until now, it remains an open question how global resources use can be reduced. Most sustainability strategies hope to decrease resource use by raising resource efficiency ("decoupling"), but so far success has been limited. During the second half of the 20th century, a relative decoupling of resource use and GDP could be observed in most industrialized countries, meaning that resource use grew at a slower pace than economic activity (GDP), i.e. material productivity grew less than GDP. Examples for strong absolute decoupling, i.e. absolute reductions of resource use coinciding with ongoing GDP growth are rare and are usually only observed during short periods of low GDP growth or economic crises (Haberl et al., 2020; Wiedenhofer et al., 2020). Since 2002, global material productivity has even declined in some regions or countries, leading to a global re-coupling of material use to GDP (Schandl et al., 2017; Krausmann et al., 2018). Clearly, the sheer magnitude of material and energy use represents a major obstacle for transformations towards sustainability (Görg et al., 2017, 2020).

An alternative analytical approach to identify options for reducing resource use which goes beyond the hope of increasing resource efficiency, is the stock-flow-service nexus (SFS-nexus; Haberl et al., 2017). The SFS-nexus focuses on the systemic interrelations between the societal services provided through material stocks and flows of resources (materials and energy) and the ensuing wastes and emissions. Services can be defined as something that societies actually demand from material stocks and resource flows (Kalt et al., 2019). Focusing on the services stocks provide, such as mobility, shelter or nutrition, it can be asked whether lower levels of resource use can be achieved by alternative options to structure the SFS-nexus. Within societies, however, the services stocks and flows provide are linked to a variety of very different outcomes creating benefits for some but also costs or disadvantages for other social groups. For instance, a new highway that enables for some people faster mobility from home to the workspace may create noise and pollution for local residents. For this reason, the societal services and the benefits (or detriments) they may provide must be scrutinized carefully.

Drawing on this debate, the aim of this contribution is to develop a framework to conceptualize the possibilities for analytically approaching the SFS-nexus and developing options of its transformation. In doing so, we integrate a refined concept of provisioning systems within the context of the SFS-nexus for analyzing opportunities but also challenges for its shaping and restructuring, i.e. for social-ecological transformations. By referring to provisioning systems, we can investigate two dimensions: a) the interlinkages between biophysical and socioeconomic processes and, even more important in our context, b) the options for (re-)shaping these systemic processes. For analyzing these options, we refer to the agency involved, i.e. the preferences, interests and the power relations of certain (individual and collective) actors, and the technical and institutional conditions that structure such agency within space and time. The interplay of actors and resources takes place through institutions, technologies, knowledge and practices (Hummel, 2008; Liehr et al., 2017), all of which are embedded within the state as a contested terrain which also stabilizes the SFS-nexus temporally. We argue that these characteristics of provisioning systems are crucial for understanding the SFS-nexus and the options for its transformation.

The paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, we present the current research on the SFS-nexus. In Section 3, we introduce different

approaches of provisioning systems and discuss their relevance for analyzing the SFS-nexus and its transformation. The fourth section refines our understanding of provisioning systems developed out of Section 3 by integrating the role of space and time and the state. Section 5 then presents our conceptual framework of how to analyze the transformation of the SFS-nexus before we draw some conclusions and develop options for further research.

2. The SFS-nexus and its challenges for transformation research

The SFS-nexus has been proposed as a conceptual approach for analyzing the interrelation between material stocks, energy and material flows, and societal services (Haberl et al., 2017). The core claim is that stocks and flows interact in providing services demanded by society and that this "triangular" conceptualization of the relations between biophysical resources and social well-being is more powerful to analyze options to reduce resource use than narrow concepts of "eco-efficiency" (e.g., energy or material required per unit of GDP). These systemic relations between stocks, flows and services are a core feature of society-nature interactions relevant to sustainability (Haberl et al., 2017; Haberl et al., 2019; see Fig. 1).

The SFS-nexus approach expands upon research on societal metabolism (Ayres and Simonis, 1994; Baccini and Brunner, 1991; Martinez-Alier, 1987; Fischer-Kowalski, 1998; Krausmann et al., 2017a; Haberl et al., 2019) by linking the increasing amount of resources used for building and using material stocks (Krausmann et al., 2018) with their role for societal development, in particular their role in shaping patterns (Weisz et al., 2015; Graedel et al., 2015) of resource use. In recent years, the crucial role of material stocks of infrastructures and buildings for resource use patterns have increasingly come into focus (Lanau et al., 2019; Wei-Qiang and Graedel, 2015; Weisz et al., 2015). Economy-wide material stock accumulation across all resource flows and consistent with harmonized methods of economy-wide material flow accounting have only recently been published (Krausmann et al., 2017b). These methods are a prerequisite for a more systematic and comprehensive approach to investigating stock-flow-relationships because they allow to consistently cover all resource flows and subsequent material stock accumulation (Krausmann et al., 2018; Wiedenhofer et al., 2019). In this paper, we introduce the concept of provisioning systems to better understand the development of material stocks in terms of the services they provide for societies, the spatial patterns involved as much as the socio-economic drivers and the power relations behind these dynamics. This is a prerequisite to determine concrete options to reduce resource use while further ensure the provision of essential societal services.

Our understanding of the SFS-nexus builds upon the energy service cascade (Kalt et al., 2019; see Fig. 2), which was developed based on the ecosystem service cascade (Potschin and Haines-Young, 2011). The energy service cascade allows for a clear distinction between the major blocks of the SFS-nexus (between stocks, functions, services and benefits) and presents a more complete systemic view of their interrelationships. Following the energy service cascade, biophysical stocks (e.g. transport infrastructure) and flows (e.g. final energy use) must be distinguished from the physical functions they perform (e.g.

Fig. 1. The stock-flow-service nexus (Haberl et al., 2017).

Fig. 2. The energy service cascade (Kalt et al., 2019: 49).

transporting goods or people), the services they provide within societies (e.g. enabling mobility), the benefits they contribute to human well-being (e.g. creating income or saving travelling time) and the individual values, attitudes or interests addressed (e.g. ensuring employment opportunities or life satisfaction; Kalt et al., 2019). Here, it is important to mention that the energy service cascade from Kalt et al. (2019) is not only an analytical tool but represents an ideal type which does not explicitly analyze power relations and their effects on the SFS-nexus (see more below on this in Section 4).

One key challenge previously identified revolves around (in-)commensurability, measurability and (languages of) valuation (Martinez-Alier, 2002). While material stocks and biophysical resource flows can be observed in a harmonized and commensurable manner, for example as metric tons of physical objects, already the functions provided by them are less commensurable and often need to be observed with specific indicators for each function (e.g. person-kilometer travelled, m^3 of temperate living space, see Kalt et al., 2019). However, services, defined as 'what is actually demanded by society', the benefits these services provide and their contributions to human well-being, are already incommensurable, possibly differ across different actor groups, and are increasingly less quantifiable due to the fact that they depend on societal interests and underlying values (Kalt et al., 2019). This means that additionally qualitative approaches and methods are needed to analyze these underlying values and societal interests, leading to broader interdisciplinary approaches (Haberl et al., 2017). In particular, the evaluation of advantages and disadvantages of existing stocks, but even more of alternative options under discussion, raises additional challenges. Very often, such advantages and disadvantages are carried out by experts (e.g. engineers or economists), but also discussed in media and civil society and assessed by local residents, users or other affected groups. Benefits are calculated differently by different scientific methods,¹ and local residents very often have profound knowledge about the advantages and disadvantages of certain stocks and the services they provide at a certain place. This is particularly relevant for an analysis of transformation options towards lower resource use because scientific methods may ignore some implications of resource use (e.g. economic valuation methods may ignore contributions to human well-being beyond monetary income generation) and miscalculate alternative options (Chan et al., 2012).

Before we further discuss the role of transformation, we need to define the two possible uses of the concept of social-ecological transformations: The first one is an analytical one, focusing on both short-term and long-term changes in societal relation to nature, with a

¹ See the debate on methodological challenges involved while measuring ecosystem services beyond monetary valuation methods: Chan et al., 2012; Gómez-Baggethun and Barton, 2013; Jax et al., 2013; Diaz et al., 2018.

strong focus on the societal metabolism and its technical, institutional, cultural and political-economic implications (see Görg et al., 2017). The second one, more recently used, is a normative and strategical approach for a deep rooted, far reaching and just transformation going perhaps beyond capitalism (e.g. Tauss, 2018). This paper shares some basic assumptions of this strategic usages, e.g. the claim that a sustainable use of material resources requires a break with the capitalist growth paradigm (e.g. Görg et al., 2020), i.e. a deep-rooted transformation. However, it is not the aim here to provide more empirical evidence for this argument, but to improve the analytical understanding while referring to the concept of provisioning system. The analytical approach also starts from the observation that such a transformation must go beyond widespread hopes in technical efficiencies as sole sustainability strategy and also needs to address the overall scale of resource use caused by production and consumption and different provisioning systems (Haberl et al., 2020; Wiedenhofer et al., 2020; Creutzig et al., 2021).

The key assertion for this paper is that an investigation of transformation options requires that the expectations of social actors, their societal interests and the power relations involved must be taken seriously. In many countries, worldwide new infrastructure projects and the construction of stocks like roads, railroads, pipelines or mining sites are highly contested and these conflicts include questions of interests and power as much as perceptions of justice and fairness in the balance of benefits and costs, including the different languages of valuation involved in these debates or conflicts (Martinez-Alier, 2002).² An option to discuss these contested issues are transdisciplinary approaches capable of investigating the knowledge claims of different actor groups related to resource flows, but also to the technologies and interests involved (Jahn et al., 2012; Hummel et al., 2017; Lang et al., 2012). To analyze in more detail why certain stocks are constructed, which services and which benefits for whom are allocated, and finally which options are available to achieve a reduction of resource use, we need an inter- and transdisciplinary approach able to investigate the processes that leads to the construction and perhaps transformation of a certain SFS-nexus. For that purpose, we refer to the concept of provisioning systems.

3. Different conceptualizations of provisioning systems

The concept of provisioning systems has been used in different research contexts and for several aims. Provisioning systems have been introduced to understand the interconnections between material and cultural dimensions of consumption and between production and consumption (Fine 2013, Bayliss et al., 2020; Mattioli et al., 2020). They

² See e.g. the atlas on global environmental justice conflicts: <https://ejatlas.org/>; Pichler et al., 2017.

have served as an approach to investigate the links between resource use, human well-being and basic needs (O'Neill et al., 2018; Brand-Correa and Steinberger, 2017; Lili, 2018). Moreover, provisioning systems represent a heuristic concept to instruct inter- and transdisciplinary research on societal relations with nature, dealing with biophysical and cultural-symbolic dimensions (Becker and Jahn, 2006). Most recently, provisioning systems are attracting increasing interest in the sustainability sciences (Fanning et al., 2020) and in the debates around demand-side contributions to climate change mitigation (Creutzig et al. 2018; 2020), where we want to contribute to and enrich the conceptual debate.

To understand better the potential of provisioning systems for analyzing the transformation options of the SFS-nexus, we draw on two main debates of provisioning systems used in inter- and transdisciplinary research, which we discuss below: ecological economics and political economy (Section 3.1) and the Frankfurt School of Social Ecology (Section 3.2). One is predominantly used in the English-speaking, the other one in the German-speaking area.

3.1. Conceptualizations from ecological economics and political economy

One of the earliest and widely received approaches in political economy with regard to the area of consumption is the Systems of Provision approach developed by Fine (2002); first presented in Fine and Leopold, 1993). It was motivated by the quest to understand consumption not only as individual behavior but to trace consumption back to production via distribution and marketing. By underlining this vertical approach to consumption, i.e. linking consumption back to production, Systems of Provision highlights the role of consumers and their practices and conceptualises structures, processes, agents/agencies and relations as essential building blocks of Systems of Provision (Fine et al., 2018).³ The Systems of Provision approach is demand-side oriented and assumes a co-management of demand on the side of consumers and providers, where “consumers and providers are both involved in managing flows of energy, water and waste” (van Vliet et al., 2005: 2). Yet, agents, acting within structures and processes can have different, competing interests (Bayliss, 2016).

Another important characteristic of Systems of Provision is that they have a cultural and a material dimension. These dimensions are different for different commodities, be it housing or water (Bayliss, 2016). Even within a broadly defined provisioning system such as food supply, several Systems of Provision can be delineated, depending on the “variations in the ways that foods are grown, cropped, processed, packaged, sold and consumed” (Leopold and Fine, 1993: 153). Connected to these material and symbolic dimensions, Fine and Leopold (1993) underline the contingencies of SoP: “Such an approach allows theory to accommodate common sense, which tells us that consumption over the past two hundred years has not proceeded smoothly upwards along a curve of constant slope; that the qualitative and quantitative impact of consumption during a period of labour market (and productive capacity) expansion may be greater than that of periods preceding or following; that the domestic consumption of coal differs significantly from the consumption of nuclear energy; and so on.” (ibid.: 23f.)

This understanding of Systems of Provision creates room for manoeuvre and allows to link changes in individual consumption patterns with changes in production and politics. Although Systems of Provision focus on individual consumption rather than e.g. on state welfare provision (and on direct consumption and thus not explicitly on

stocks, i.e. material entities that deliver services for societies), it does not limit their analysis to individual decision making: having the individual as a starting point, the approach considers also the societal structures behind it. Moreover, it underlines the role of collective actors and institutions and therefore goes beyond individual consumption behavior.

Systems of Provision also deals with the role of the state, which shapes the entire chain of provision. The state defines, for example, who has access to water, it provides subsidies and is responsible for spatial planning, land tenure or social housing systems. In the course of neoliberalization, the role of the state has changed, i.e. the shift from state provision to privatization and financialization has major relevance for the provision of services; the same for the transformation back to community-based ownership (Bayliss, 2016). Recently, Systems of Provision have been applied to explore the role of financialization in housing (Robertson, 2016) or the water supply in Great Britain (Bayliss, 2014), examining different kinds of tenure systems, allowing differentiating between countries and analyzing core agents such as financiers, landowners, producers, labour, the state and consumers. These empirical cases make Systems of Provision not only context specific, considering space and time, but show that the governance of Systems of Provision – publicly or privately – affects consumers (Robertson, 2016). However, the role of the state in Systems of Provision is not well enough researched and theoretically not conceptualized.

Recently, Systems of Provision has been integrated into social-ecological research. The research project “Living well within limits” (LiLi, 2018) uses the term provisioning systems in interdisciplinary work, in particular for linking biophysical input to debates on human needs. It addresses how basic human needs can be met within the planetary boundaries, integrating different ‘footprint’ indicators and including social boundaries as the “safe and just space” framework. Here, provisioning systems “is the broad term used to describe the chain linking the production, distribution and consumption of the goods and services through which human needs are met” (LiLi, 2018). Provisioning systems are framed as intermediary between the biophysical inputs and the social outcomes. A differentiation is made between physical and social provisioning systems, i.e. infrastructure, technology, land use, supply chains on the one hand and state, markets, communities, institutions, norms, culture and distribution on the other hand. According to O'Neill et al. (2018) both physical and social provisioning systems need to be re-structured and improved to achieve a good life for all. For the operationalization of their empirical research, the project integrates Systems of Provision into their conceptual framework, guiding the analysis of provisioning systems (LiLi, 2018).

Drawing on a need-centered understanding of human well-being, Brand-Correa and Steinberger (2017) follow the eudaimonic (‘flourishing’) tradition. This means that the understanding of well-being is not focused on individual behavior through market consumption but includes social and political systems. Based on Doyal and Gough (1991) and Max-Neef (1991) who identifies nine needs (subsistence, protection, affection, understanding, participation, leisure, creation, identity and freedom) and four categories (being, having, doing, interacting), they argue that “there are a finite number of self-evident (i.e. universal, recognizable by anyone), incommensurable (thus satiable, irreducible and non-substitutable) and non-hierarchical needs” (Brand-Correa and Steinberger, 2017: 46). The so-called “need satisfiers (ibid.) can vary between individuals and cultures, but arguable have certain universal characteristics that maybe measured empirically” (O'Neill et al., 2018: 88). The integration of participatory processes shall ensure that the specific needs of the community are considered.

New research has further developed the question on provisioning systems (Fanning et al., 2020). However, the heuristic approach does not specifically focus on the transformation of the physical (in terms of stocks) and socially contested provisioning systems.

³ To analyze Systems of Provision, Fine (2013) developed the so-called 10 Cs, which encompass the following dimensions: Constructed, Construed, Commodified, Conforming, Contextual, Contradictory, Chaotic, Closed, Contested and Collective. To give an example, one can draw on the different Cs to Contextualize research e.g. on financialization of housing when analyzing its Commodification in Great Britain.

3.2. Conceptualizations from the Frankfurt School of Social Ecology

A second important approach dealing with provisioning systems comes from the Frankfurt School of Social Ecology, which designs provisioning systems as a conceptual model with heuristic and analytical functions for operationalizing transdisciplinary research processes (Hummel et al., 2017; Liehr et al., 2017). This operationalization supports outlining the research problem and structuring the research process (Liehr et al., 2017). In this understanding, provisioning systems provide a framework for empirically and analytically approaching the regulation and transformation of societal relations to nature. Accordingly, provisioning systems link natural to social structures and processes and address the interplay of the material world, of ecosystems and other resources, and societal processes like social practices or institutions. As a model, the provisioning system concept is in principle scale independent but best suited and mostly applied for meso-level studies. On that scale, it is easier to set a clear framework for the research question in a manner that reflects an adequate level of complexity of the social and ecological processes involved, and to apply appropriate transdisciplinary methods. For example, the Frankfurt approach was empirically applied for analyzing the impact of environmental and in particular climate change on migration in the Sahel region, using Bayesian Belief Networks as modelling approach (Drees and Liehr, 2015).

Provisioning systems are embedded in an understanding of society as constitutively linked to or interacting with nature.⁴ The concept of social-ecological systems addresses these interlinkages between the material-energetic dimension (i.e. resource flows and the building of stocks) and the cultural-symbolic one (i.e. the cultural meaning and social dynamics), which together represents how societies are linked to the material world. Here, Becker and Schramm (2002) speak of different forms with which societies materially regulate and culturally symbolize their natural conditions. Similar to other approaches of social-ecological systems research (Binder et al., 2013), the interlinkages are conceptualized as complex adaptive systems that link societal to natural structures and processes (Gunderson et al., 2002; Schlüter et al., 2019a; Schlüter et al., 2019b; Schlüter et al., 2014). The core components of these systems are characterized as hybrid, meaning that they exhibit aspects of both, the social and natural side. This hybrid character becomes exemplarily clear looking on interactions like irrigation, harvesting or heating as all of them are phenomena in which human action and natural processes are closely interwoven. The provisioning system approach has, for example, recently been used to address problems of the interplay between demography and sustainable provisioning of water in Germany, or between environmental change and migration in West Africa (Hummel, 2008).

The hybrid core components of the social-ecological systems can be grasped analytically and empirically through four constitutive dimensions with key importance for shaping the strongly interrelated societal and natural structures and processes ('Gestaltungsdimensionen'): institutions, technology, practices and knowledge (Hummel, 2008: 48; Hummel et al., 2013: 117). The term 'institutions' addresses the fields of economy, politics, law and culture that create a regulatory system of rules for action with regard to the use of ecosystem services. 'Technology' refers to all man-made material structures and developments that are designed and applied in order to interfere with ecosystem functions with the aim of making specific services available for use. Societal 'practices' represent routinised types and patterns of behavior regarding the use of ecosystem services in their material or

symbolic relevance. Finally, 'knowledge' comprises all forms of understanding by scientists and non-scientists referring to nature-society interrelations (Liehr et al., 2017). These shaping dimensions open a door for empirical investigations how the dynamic interaction of ecosystem functions (of which resources are a part) and actors (of which users are a part) is organized as a provisioning system (see Fig. 3).

Similar to the energy service cascade, the provisioning system approach was developed further with a focus on ecosystem services and biodiversity (Mehring et al., 2017; Liehr et al., 2017). Applying it to societal metabolism in general and the SFS-nexus in particular requires further adaptations. Provisioning is defined as "any benefit societies draw from natural resources" (Hummel et al., 2017: 9) and provisioning systems were used to analyze social-ecological systems and e.g. the impact of societies on biodiversity and subsequent consequences for ecosystem services, for example, via land-use or water-extraction. They are "regulated by societies, and at the same time they depend on natural conditions and are affected by their viability" (Hummel et al., 2011: 9). Provisioning systems are mostly conceptualized in a selective, problem-oriented way. The advantage of this concept is that the respective resource flow can be studied in an analytical way 'as they are' (including their institutions, practices, knowledge and technology) apart from any normative assumption on what basic conditions are or should be.

Unlike the Systems of Provision approach, this approach on provisioning systems focuses directly on societal needs and services. Although it addresses the question of basic human needs, central for societal reproduction, it states that "these processes always exist, for the socialized individual, only in culturally and thus socially interpreted forms" (Hummel et al., 2017: 6). Needs are never culturally neutral and must be scrutinized in particular regarding the resources required to fulfill them. Moreover, certain stocks and the services they enable do not only provide benefits, but also costs or disadvantages which is important for an analysis of the SFS-nexus. For example, certain options to provide mobility (e.g. cars and roads) do not only create mobility services, but also endanger neighboring residents through noise, elevated risk of accidents or pollution, and may even be detrimental for users (e.g. due to lack of physical activity). It is therefore important to critically scrutinize the concrete regulation of the SFS-nexus through provisioning systems, the benefits and disadvantages they provide for certain people or groups within societies. This is in particular relevant concerning the spatial and temporal patterns in which they are arranged because they determine both who benefits (e.g. access) and who is affected by the detriments. Furthermore, the approach does not only look at the 'public' (water, food, housing, energy) but also at the 'private' sphere (reproductive work, care).

Several knowledge types are required to evaluate benefits or costs, including different scientific disciplines, which may well contradict each other (e.g. economic valuation and ecological accounting), but also non-scientific knowledge (e.g. local experiences and tacit knowledge), based sometimes on cultural perception (see FN 1 for the discussion on ecosystem services). Thus, to assess the services provided and the societal needs they (supposedly) fulfill, different types of knowledge must be integrated. Beyond scientific and non-scientific knowledge, further types of knowledge can be distinguished (system, orientation and transformation knowledge) and a transdisciplinary mode of research is required (Jahn et al., 2012; Liehr et al., 2017; Dressel et al., 2014; Pohl and Hirsch Hadorn, 2006).

The transdisciplinary research process begins with a societally relevant problem area (Pohl and Hirsch Hadorn, 2006), which is jointly addressed by societal and scientific actors, who then transform the problem into weakly and more strongly structured objects of integration and investigation, so-called boundary and epistemic objects (Jahn et al., 2012). The disciplinary and interdisciplinary research tasks are then to be defined and implemented and, for the final phase of the transdisciplinary research process, the integration and preparation of products for the respective further processes in the social and scientific field should take place. Such a transdisciplinary research aims to tackle

⁴ For our purpose here in this paper, it is not necessary to deal with the conceptual and ontological differences between the Viennese and the Frankfurt approach to Social Ecology in detail. Central concepts like societal relations to nature, coming from very specific theoretical traditions, will not be elaborated; see for their conceptual background: Becker and Jahn, 2006; Görg, 2011.

Fig. 3. Conceptualization of provisioning systems by the Frankfurt School (Mehring et al., 2017; Liehr et al., 2017).

specific societal problems, and hence needs to proceed in a problem-oriented manner.

3.3. Main takeaways for the analysis of the transformation of the SFS-nexus

We summarize shortly the main insights of the two approaches for our discussion on the analytical conceptualization of social-ecological transformations of the SFS-nexus. All approaches emphasize the interplay of biophysical and societal processes, referring to a material and symbolic dimension. Further, they combine structural/systemic and actor-oriented approaches. These approaches can guide our analysis of the SFS-nexus in a complementary way, underlining the barriers and options of transformation.

Systems of Provision represents an informative starting point for the analyses guided by political economy concepts seeking to understand the analytically the social-ecological transformation and its barriers, whereas the strength of the Frankfurt School of Social Ecology is the analysis of the shaping dimensions. Systems of Provision highlights the role of power relations as well as the contingencies of transformation processes, i.e. that there is no compulsory linear development of resource flows. By embedding the role of the consumer into production processes and underlining the role of the state, where a greater conceptual understanding of the latter is fruitful, it puts light on structural factors that shape the SFS-nexus. The Frankfurt School of Social Ecology, in turn, provides points of references for understanding the options how the SFS-nexus can be shaped, focusing on knowledge, technology, actors and institutions including the actors' interests and power relations. Importantly, it highlights that needs and services are never neutral and it further emphasizes that the transdisciplinary is crucial for shaping society-nature relations.

4. Further refining the concept of provisioning systems

While our understanding of provisioning systems builds on the two approaches outlined above, two crucial dimensions are still missing to fully grasp the transformation of the SFS-nexus: (1) the notion of space and time, (2) the concept of the state as a conflictive terrain. We will explain them in the next section before introducing our understanding of provisioning systems which we then use to examine the transformation of the SFS-nexus.

4.1. Space and time

Stocks are always spatially and temporally specific, indeed the specification of the particular point in time at which it is measured is constitutive for the very notion of a stock variable. To analyze the SFS-nexus and the societal services involved, we enrich the available approaches to provisioning systems with the notion of space and time.

The need for considering the spatial and temporal dimension has been prominently discussed in critical social sciences at least since the debate on capitalist globalization in the 1990ies (Brenner et al., 2003; Wissen, 2011). Globalization itself has been conceptualized as a process of spatial reorganization and re-scaling, where other scales, in particular the national, but also urban, regional and local scales and the interdependencies between them, do not disappear but were reshaped by altered power relations (Brenner, 2004; Brenner et al., 2003). The spatial rescaling involved in globalization processes reshapes social relations at certain places with strong consequences for the stocks and flows of resources. Some regions, e.g. former centers of industrialization and societal development like Detroit, were excluded from the globalization process and experienced an unprecedented decline resulting in large infrastructures now wasted, while others became central and needs additional stocks (Wang et al., 2017). Because of the interdependencies of global, national, regional and local scales, Erik Swyngedouw (1997) denoted the interlinkages between global and local dimensions of social and ecological processes as “glocalization”. The scalar reorganization of societal processes became a major topic of human geography and influenced also other debates in social sciences (Wissen, 2011; Brenner et al., 2003). Two dimensions were crucial in this regard: the power relations involved in spatial reorganization and the link to the specific capitalist nature of globalization.

The latter was emphasized by David Harvey which we draw on because his understanding of spatial reorganization has several dimensions with different implications for the SFS-nexus and its transformation. Stocks can represent what Harvey called “spatial fix” and “temporal fix” (Harvey, 2001, 2013). From the early 1980ies onwards, he has analyzed the spatial reorganization of capitalism coining the terms. Harvey figuratively describes his notion of fix: “I note, for example, that capitalism has to fix space (in immovable structures of transport and communication nets, as well as in built environments of factories, roads, houses, water supplies, and other physical infrastructures) in order to overcome space (achieve a liberty of movement through low transport and communication costs).” (Harvey, 2003: 116) He distinguished two meanings of fixes. One is related to “a certain portion of the total capital (...) literally fixed on the land in some

physical form” (Harvey, 2013: 115) whereas the other, a “spatial-temporal fix”, is a more metaphorical use of the term fix denoting the above-mentioned crisis solution by geographical expansion, which can only be temporarily successful (ibid.; Harvey, 2001).

Both meanings of fixes are linked in a manner that is very instructive for discussing the SFS-nexus. While the first notion of spatial fix represents a direct entry point for a spatially explicit analysis of biophysical stocks, the second is also insightful. It mentions that within capitalism, the function of infrastructure development in its spatial dimensions follows a logic of capital accumulation and thus has only a temporary existence. In this sense, the functional character of stocks and flows is conceptualized not only by the functions, services and benefits they provide to (certain) people, but also by the internal characteristics of the social system involved. “This leads to one of the central contradictions of capital: that it has to build a fixed space (or ‘landscape’) necessary for its own functioning at a certain point in its history only to have to destroy that space (and devalue much of the capital invested therein) at a later point in order to make way for a new ‘spatial fix’ (openings for fresh accumulation in new spaces and territories) at a later point in its history” (Harvey, 2003: 116). Here, functional perspectives of capitalist dynamics link the creation and transformation of infrastructures or stocks to something Joseph Schumpeter has called a creative destruction: that capitalism destroys and reconfigures previous economic orders in order to clear the ground for the creation of new wealth (Schumpeter, 1942). Its destruction is to some degree unavoidable for the creation of new stocks and functional for capital accumulation and economic growth.

One important blind spot of Harvey’s analysis is the missing conceptualisation of the state within these processes. The state, however is important, when the concrete implications for the biophysical stocks and flows involved shall be analyzed. Whereas Harvey in general acknowledges that spatial and spatio-temporal fixes are created by economic and extra-economic forces, i.e. by capital accumulation and by political factors, a coherent integration of this economic perspective with extra-economic factors such as politics, the territorial character of the national states and other factors that may influence social conflicts is missing (Jessop, 2004). For an analysis of the SFS-nexus and its transformation through provisioning systems, however, it is decisive to better integrate both dimensions to understand how transformations are shaped by conflicts with spatial and temporal determinants and how they are inscribed in political and institutional regulations. This leads to the territorial logic of states as we will explain below.

4.2. The state as a conflictive terrain⁵

States are not merely actors, but represent a terrain of social struggles. They are shaped by the interests and power relations of societal actors. Following Nicos Poulantzas (1978), power relations of social forces are inscribed in state institutions and strategies. As we have seen in Section 2, the Systems of Provision concept refers to the state, but without conceptualizing it carefully. Also, the state and the “extra-economic” political logic it represents are important in the rescaling of spatial patterns and the logic of territorialization, mentioned by Harvey. Yet, as Jessop (2002, 2004) correctly emphasizes, the state is not an “extra-economic” entity but rather its precondition: within capitalism, economic activities need to be ensured through a political and legal order. As emphasized by the concept of political economy, economic

⁵ We are fully aware that the concept of the state is strongly related to the Northern industrialized countries in the West and that in the Global South or in the East states have only limited sovereignty. They are shaped by their role in the global economy, e.g. the extractivist state in Latin America (Swampa, 2019) or the oligarchic state in Ukraine (Plank, 2016). Nevertheless, even in times of neoliberal globalization, an internationalised state emerged as a multi-scalar terrain where social-ecological conflicts are inscribed into state institutions at local, regional, national and international level (Brand et al., 2008).

activities are always shaped and secured by a legal or institutional framework, established and guaranteed by the state.

As mentioned above, capitalist globalization does not mean that the (national) state disappears but it changes (Hirsch et al., 2001; Jessop, 2002; Brand et al., 2008). For our purpose, two dimensions are particularly relevant: the re-scaling of statehood to other scales (in particular to supranational such as the European Union or regional levels; see Brenner, 2004) and its neoliberal reorganization as a national competition state (Hirsch, 1995). This has important implications for the building of stocks, where there are different spatial strategies that guide infrastructure development. Certain concepts have changed their very meaning during the 20th century dramatically. For example, the concept of “Daseinsvorsorge” (‘services of general interest’) in Germany, which seems to denote a service-oriented concept, has changed its concrete meaning several times. It was developed as a Nazi-strategy to legitimize a war of conquest and spatial expansion. After World War II, it represented an important element of the post-war welfare state to provide similar ways of living in the whole national territory. Later on, it became an element of European integration as part of a neoliberal competition strategy enabling certain regional developments (Folkers, 2017). “Each regime exhibited a unique relation between infrastructure and state power: the totalitarian Nazi state mobilized infrastructure for war and genocide, the liberal democratic welfare state developed infrastructure to increase prosperity and the neoliberal warranty state now tries to secure infrastructure in public-private partnerships.” (ibid.: 870).

In a similar way, current infrastructure strategies (the “infrastructure moment”, see Bridge et al., 2018) must be analyzed critically concerning its geopolitical content, the uneven development and the inequalities involved, and the political imaginaries applied (“political dreamscapes”; Bridge et al., 2018).⁶ Very important examples in this regard are the historical Marshall plan and, more recently, the Chinese Belt and Road Initiative. Whereas the first was an important element of the establishment of the welfare state after World War I (but see also Swampa (2020) concerning the resource consensus and alternative narratives within extractivist countries), the last must be analyzed as both, as a search for a boost for Chinese domestic and global capitalism (a spatio-temporal fix after Harvey) and at the same time as a geopolitical strategy to improve the relative political power of China.

As a consequence, the building of stocks can neither be reduced to a strategy to serve people’s needs, nor be only analyzed in a normative way by focusing on the services they provide. We find, that when analyzing the transformation of the SFS-nexus, a multi-scalar concept of statehood must be applied to understand the challenges and conflicts involved.

5. Analyzing social-ecological transformations of the SFS-nexus

Building on the SFS-nexus and the provisioning systems approaches introduced above, refined by critical human geography and materialist state theory, we propose the following conceptual framework for research on the transformation of the SFS-nexus (Fig. 4). For such an integrated approach, it is particularly challenging to combine quantitative analyses of the biophysical basis of provisioning systems with qualitative approaches to better analyze the interplay of social structures and agency. This implies the consideration of societal actors and their interests, of functions and services, of institutions, technology, practices and knowledge, but also the (re-)structuring of power relations affecting the various components of the SFS-nexus. In the following, the building blocks of such an inter- and transdisciplinary approach and the analytical and methodical challenges involved are discussed in more

⁶ See also other contributions in the special issue of Energy Research and Social Sciences on “Energy infrastructures and the fate of the nation”: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/energy-research-and-social-science/vol/41/suppl/C>.

Fig. 4. Our novel conceptual framework for analyzing the transformation of the SFS-nexus as part of a provisioning system.

detail.

5.1. Proposal for a novel conceptual framework

Our novel conceptual framework uses the building blocks of the SFS-nexus and the energy service cascade but re-orders them horizontally. The reason behind is that we want to avoid the impression that there is a linear causality between the building blocks. Similar to the ecosystem service cascade,⁷ however, we need to distinguish between a causal and a normative-defining interplay between the building blocks.

To deliver a biophysical outcome for societies, benefits, services and also the functions of certain stocks need to be *valued*, *defined* or *selected*: without a societal selection, some housings may no longer provide a function nor a service for societies but represent abandoned housing stocks. The same holds for services: without a demand from society, railroads or tracks, may no longer provide mobility services but become scrap. This is even more important for the benefits provided by services, because, as we already mentioned earlier, they are clearly dependent on valuations by specific actors or groups, and the same services may provide benefits for some individuals or groups and disadvantages for others. Thus, both directions are equally important: Resources flow physically into stocks or are used to operate stocks; they provide functions, services and benefits and satisfy or contest the interests and needs of the actors. Actors, in turn, manifest their interests and values, define benefits or complain about disadvantages they see related to certain services, and thereby rely on stocks and resource flows.

The already explained cascade of stepwise dependencies is determined in our concept by a higher-level feedback relationship in which the individual steps of the cascade are embedded: On the one hand, interests and values provide the basis for what is identified and constructed as stocks by the actors. What counts as stocks and how they are shaped depends crucially on economic conditions, socio-cultural

meanings and socio-political framework settings, which form the background of interests and values. On the other hand, it is precisely these interests and values that are significantly co-determined by the possibilities that the stocks offer to the actors on the basis of the available resources. In other words, the stocks enable and constrain the range of interests and values of the actors. Understanding this feedback relationship requires more than just looking at the situation at a given point in time; it is shaped by path dependencies, so that historical developments also play an important role in grasping it.

To better understand how the SFS-nexus is constituted and how it can be transformed, we propose to use our conceptual framework in two ways. One way is to focus on the SFS-nexus and the provisioning systems as they are, analyzing the role of the state and examining the barriers and options of transformation, using conflicts as an entry point for the analysis. The other way to approach the transformation of the SFS-nexus is to inquire in a transdisciplinary manner how the nexus could and should be transformed. Here, we suggest to start the analysis by focusing on the services which should be provided. This second part acknowledges the role of non-scientific, of practical or tacit knowledge, in the evaluation and transformation of the SFS-nexus. For the transdisciplinary analysis, we do not provide a methodological in-depth guidance concerning the processes but rather aim at providing theoretical conceptual grounding to think about options of how the SFS-nexus can be shaped.

5.2. Key considerations about the role of the state and the transformation of the SFS-nexus

Conceptualizing the state as a contested terrain opens up an understanding of social-ecological transformation that focuses on conflict and barriers as much as on power relations as one reason for their existence. The state plays a decisive role in the construction and handling of stocks. Its decisions are crucial for the design, planning and approval of many material stocks, in particular buildings and infrastructures, even if they are partially or fully owned and carried out by private investors. The construction, maintenance and disposal of these stocks, in particular when they happen to be large infrastructures, are often highly contested due to their relevance for societal development patterns and the spatial and economic inequalities involved. Hence, it is a political question

⁷ Within the ecosystem service cascade, a causal and a normative-defining interplay needs to be distinguished, as Jax (2004, 201) and Spangenberg et al. (2014) have shown. Whereas only the causal interplay follows a systematic of arrows from the top (biophysical functions) to the bottom (human values), other arrows goes from the bottom to the top by dealing with valuation and definition of certain benefits, services or functions.

which options are preferred and which decision are finally made, even if economic calculations are considered. To address these conflicts, we have to scrutinize the contribution of specific stocks to the benefits or the losses of certain parts of the population, potentially split into different societal groups. Usually, they provide these services and benefits only for certain groups, at least if their advantages (benefits) and disadvantages (e.g. costs) are closely scrutinized. The state is also relevant for private investments in, for example, housing or factory sites, as they need political and legal regulations (e.g. spatial planning (Plank et al., 2021), land tenure (Plank, 2016)). So overall, the question of shaping the SFS-nexus, is a question of further societal development and thus goes far beyond e.g. technological innovations or sectoral policies.

One particular relevant approach to investigate empirically are conflicts about stock development and the barriers they represent for using less resources, is historical materialist policy and politics analysis (HMPA; Brand, 2013; Forschungsgruppe "Staatsprojekt Europa", 2014.). It assumes that the state as a specific social relation is required to stabilize contradictory and conflict driven capitalist societies. The state is conceptualized as a kind of domination which socioeconomic interests where the power relations involved are inscribed and sustained for a while. Stocks are thus part of a certain mode of regulation, which provide the necessary precondition for an economically stable accumulation regime (as the regulation theory puts it, see Jessop, 2002; Esser, 1994, Brand et al., 2008). Following this approach, the relative consistency and durability of a historical form of capitalism depends on the formation of a mode of regulation which enables social conflicts to remain relatively compatible with the valorization process of capital, which is materialized in the accumulation regime. For this to be the case, not only must the general orientations for societal development be shared (e.g. the welfare-state class compromise, the neoliberal market and competition model), but terrains must also be defined and accepted by the most important actors on which political and social struggles can be fought out without resulting in fundamental interruptions to the accumulation process. At the same time, the overall process remains crisis driven and contested and thus a destruction of established stock takes place on a regular base. However, this also provides opportunities for the reshaping or the transformation of the SFS-nexus.

A major focus regarding the obstacles and options for social-ecological transformations is on the interests and power constellations that emerge and the types of compromises institutionalized in the state at a certain scale (e.g. at national, supranational – EU – level or within a city). Societal interests are inscribed in different ways into the state as a terrain of conflicting interests (see also Mattioli et al., 2020). That implies that the state secures certain interests (e.g. in Germany where certain industrial sectors like the car industry are supported through certain infrastructures like highways without any speed limits (Neuerer and Schneider, 2019) and leaves others out (mobility needs of older people in rural areas (Abern and Hine, 2012). This affects the spatial dimensions, the scale of action of certain actors: some of them act more globally-oriented, with only limited control by the state, some are nationally anchored and others are more local groups. Regarding the spatial dimension, it is important to scrutinize the established spatial structures (e.g. of cities) and analyze actors acting on other spatial scales (e.g. transnational corporations or supranational institutions like the EU) play a crucial role (as e.g. in the building of a Transnational European Transport network (TET-N) (European Commission, 2021) or concerning the role of IT-companies for urban restructuring (for an analysis on the role of the state in urban restructuring see Adisson, 2017). Such spatial restructuring raises tensions between different interests and stimulates conflicts on a regular basis which may function as entry point for an empirical analysis.

Examples for such conflict studies are analyses of counter-movements fighting against privatization which were triggered by globalization such as the "water wars" in Cochabamba (Swyngedouw, 2004). The quest for a re-communalization in many parts of the world (The Foundational Economy Collective, 2018) or the quest for

democratization of energy supply in Berlin (Moss et al., 2015) show as well the conflictive interlinkages of spatial scales. Moss et al. (2015) have demonstrated for the German "Energiewende" ('energy transition') that struggles within and between the different levels of statehood, the national, the regional (the German 'Länder') and the communities, must be analyzed carefully and that questions of ownership (in particular after the neoliberal privatization of many municipal infrastructural facilities) and institutional change, but also the technologies involved, plays a decisive role here. Such past conflicts are inscribed in institutional settings that may become contested in future conflicts as well.

Different understandings of time influence the state and its spatial and temporal fixes. First, we need to consider that the life cycle of different stocks differs (e.g. for housing, life cycles are different for concrete, wood or brick as well as their life time (Thomsen and van der Flier, 2011; Wuyts et al., 2019). Second, the temporal dimension plays out when analyzing the exclusion or inclusion of certain services (e.g. as a preference for other services – private vs. public transport). Here, the time when the stock was built matters: was it under the welfare state or the competition state (with the latter fostering privatization)? How does the state value the stock built? (Hassler, 2010). A current example for maintaining stocks and mobility services in special times of Covid-19 are the railways or the public transport even if not intensively used. Third, time is important regarding the coordination of provisioning system, which is required for structural change. For example, technological or infrastructural developments do not work as intended if governance structures or knowledge structures are not changed accordingly.

The spatio-temporal fix expresses itself also in increasing extractivism, which deepens global inequalities. Resource extraction does often not take place because there is a need for it, in terms of the amount of stocks for the people living at the places, where extractivism happens (Swampa, 2020, Jaitner, 2014). Fanning et al. (2020) speak, in this case, of "appropriating systems" to underline that societal needs are not fulfilled but that these systems are motivated by the appropriation of rents. We think that it is necessary to dedicate our attention for empirical analysis also to these contested cases. Since we live in a globalized world, e.g. even local infrastructure projects depend on "glocalized" resource use. So it is crucial to examine where the resource come from, which are used to fuel the SFS-nexus (Dorninger et al., 2021; Mayer et al., 2017; Schaffartzik et al., 2019).

Even though the fixes in Harvey's sense remain socially contested, at some point and for some time the contested character is suppressed by the political dimension incarnated into the state. These resulting lock-in effects create path dependencies and are linked to the establishment of stocks (Seto et al., 2016) and the analysis of development pathways (Edwards, 2003). For instance, highways built foster the mobility of cars and not of railways. Yet, stocks have only a temporary existence and need maintenance through reworking, repair or recycling of their biophysical components, which is also contested between vested interests on a regular basis: should a local government provide resources to maintain and innovate an existing system of public transport, should it be substituted by an alternative system (e.g. private transport), who should pay the costs of this change and of infrastructures that are no longer required – what are the implication for resource use for maintenance, replacement or recycling (Haas et al., 2015; Krausmann et al., 2018; Wiedenhofer et al., 2019)?

Although the creative destruction (Schumpeter, 1942) is important for the circulation of capital, not everything is destroyed with the next fix. Biophysically, the next fix actually very often adds on top of the last one whereas the former fixes remains. From there, very different developments may occur: Examples are the energetic renovation of buildings without constructing the buildings from scratch, which is more resource efficient in terms of building material requirements, but often more cost intensive and can be less effective in terms of energy efficiency standards that are achieved (Röck et al., 2020; Ürges-Vorsatz et al., 2020). Other problems are offered by housing and urban infrastructure services in certain areas: After the collapse of local economies,

housing availability as well as municipal sewages and drinking water supply very often are totally oversized and cause additional problems (see the concept of shrinking cities; Kabisch et al., 2006; Deilmann et al., 2010). Another example is urban sprawl, where stagnating urban centers and growing suburban areas result in higher traffic and more environmental problems, which then need to be addressed via compact “smart” urban development strategies (Artmann et al., 2019).

To overcome lock-ins is challenging in economic, political and social terms. In particular, economic key sectors in certain national economies like extractive industries in developing or emerging economies or the car industry in some industrialized countries provide huge challenges as these economies are closely linked to a specific socio-economic growth paradigm and the specific interest coalitions behind (Lamb and Minx, 2020; Brototi and Schaffartzik, 2021). An analysis of such lock-ins must refer to the actors and the power relations involved (e.g. see the studies on unions as actors of societal transformations, Niedermoser, 2017). To open up space for renegotiating such interest coalition, actors like social movements may play an important role (see e.g. the role of the Fridays for Future for the negotiation of the European Green Deal (Stuart et al., 2020)). Overall, it is important to point out that it is a contingent question and it depends on the power relations involved whether the lock-in can be preserved or not.

5.3. Key considerations for a transdisciplinary analysis of the SFS-nexus

For the definition of alternative options, a transdisciplinary approach that also addresses the transformation of structural societal condition to provide solutions towards sustainable resource use is decisive. The determination of infrastructure projects, for example, regularly lead to debate and conflicts, because this is not a purely factual process. It rather includes societal values and interests which must be acknowledged (Pichler et al., 2016). Value judgements and the economic and societal interests involved can best be addressed by a participatory approach intended to link scientific expertise from different disciplines to stakeholder perspectives and the knowledge of practitioners in a transparent manner.

The options for (re-)shaping these systemic processes shall be discussed with a large variety of stakeholders. Their integration with various types of knowledge shall ensure that commonly created knowledge is effective and essential, enhancing the probability of implementing innovative and sustainable solutions. This requires a joint effort by stakeholders, which might be challenging to achieve if the SFS-nexus discussed is contested and a joint problem statement is not agreed upon. Stakeholders should come from different groups, i.e. state administration, civil society, expert organization and science from different disciplines dependent on the concrete research questions. Also, stakeholders should represent the spatial scale investigated (e.g. the local community, the city, the nation state, the European Union) and ideally stakeholders from other relevant spatial scales should be included.

Unlike the analysis of the state in time and space outlined above, which starts with the analysis of conflicts, the entry point of the transdisciplinary analysis are the services as they form the central interface between societal demands and natural capacities. What service shall be provided, on what scale, for what time, for whom using what kind and what amount of resources? To make it more concrete and referring to the example of mobility as service, we suggest the following guiding questions for a first step in the transdisciplinary process:

- Which services (e.g. mobility) are provided by certain kinds of infrastructures and for which activities (commuter or leisure traffic, shopping, etc.)? Who benefits from them, who is burdened? What are cross-cutting services (e.g. housing) or issues (e.g. spatial planning) influencing the need for these services (e.g., stimulated by certain kind of urban development; moving to the hinterland, urban sprawl, new industrial or shopping areas etc.)?

- What are the implications of certain kind of transport infrastructures and the (mobility) services they provide in terms of the resources needed for utilizing, maintaining existing or building up new infrastructures?
- How should decision-making for (mobility) services that need (transport) infrastructures and investments be designed in the future in order to reduce the resources flows and stocks? How should existing methods and processes of decision making be changed?
- Are there alternatives for providing (mobility) services with lower resource use? What are major options and obstacles for implementing such alternatives? How can options be implemented and obstacles be overcome?

Also, being explicit about the actors, the actor’s constellation and their relation to each other is also crucial for the transdisciplinary analysis. Actors include interest groups like business groups or trade unions, political parties, NGOs or social movements. Furthermore, it is important to examine implicit expectations or routines, practices, which need to be made explicit to open up room for alternative options for service provisions. Questions of knowledge, technological use and institutional regulation must be made transparent and unveil vested interests or hidden agendas to identify options for reshaping an existing nexus. The power relations and the specific regulations behind, which safeguard or support the SFS-nexus, e.g. specific property rights often inscribed in certain state regulation must be scrutinized.

To better understand which options for reshaping are on the table and pushed by certain actors we need a close observation of them because they can act towards ‘doing more with less’. The actors are linked to the *practices*⁸ (routinised behavior, e.g. concerning mobility), the *technologies* (e.g. engines and the resource needed for their operation), the *institutions* (that regulate e.g. the traffic system) and the *knowledge* claims involved (e.g. concerning the technical and scientific expertise involved in the definition of services and alternative options, but also from local residents with their practical experiences). Highlighting these ‘shaping dimensions’ allows us to analyze how the SFS-nexus is shaped by certain technologies or institutions, but also the practices and the knowledge of certain actors (including but also beyond individuals). These dimensions invite asking, for example, which actors or groups of actors with their respective (competing) interests and values demand which services, and which benefits or disadvantages are provided and for whom. It helps identifying how different services depend on each other (e.g. urban patterns, housing and mobility). These building blocks are embedded within wider societal structures and are mediated through different types of knowledge, practices, technologies and institutions, which need to be investigated. Important structural conditions for further transformations are institutional conditions like ownership or property rights, in particular the question of private property rights or problems of spatial planning and land use conflicts (Plank et al., 2021); all these are defined by the state.

For the second step, in the transdisciplinary analysis, we propose guiding questions which are centered around the actors but also address their practices, knowledge, technologies, institutions:

- Who values what? Who defines? Benefits and services are not given but must be defined and will be defined differently by different actor (groups), often implicitly (e.g. linked to a certain belief system or habitus) but sometimes explicitly (e.g. concerning costs and new societal challenges like digitalisation or climate change). The process of defining and valuing is deeply connected to the institutions of a society, in which its moral-ethical patterns of meaning, the power structures, the prevailing economic rules and its social constitution are expressed.

⁸ For a heuristic approach on the SFS-nexus that focusses on practices see Haberl et al., 2021.

- Who selects? Who controls? What is demanded by services is controlled by different kinds of ownership or property rights (public, private, commons), including formal (e.g. legal) or informal (e.g. customary law) institutions and the regulations associated with them. Equally relevant are the available technologies and the (expert) knowledge about their use, but also about a sufficient understanding of the system and the potential of the services.
- Who shapes? Alternative options for service provision and a constructive determination can be developed in light of their implications for the SFS-nexus but must be scrutinized concerning their feasibility in terms of all four shaping dimensions. Regarding the institutions, interest structures and power relations with the trade-offs involved have to be considered. In addition, it must be examined which technologies are available, whether the knowledge is sufficient for design, and where there is a demand for further knowledge, e.g. for an assessment of the societal and ecological impacts of shaping interventions. Finally, there is also a need for those actors who are in a position to implement corresponding design practices.

The transdisciplinary analysis is context-sensitive and often related to a certain region but may be influenced by societal (e.g. globalization, Europeanization) or biophysical (e.g. climate change) processes at higher scales or may differ even in a certain region (e.g. a city) in terms of impacts at local scale. For this reason, cross-scale interlinkages have to be considered as much as the temporal dimension such as the history of a certain stock and its development over time.

6. Conclusions

The Great Acceleration of resource use is one of the major driving forces of current unsustainability (Steffen et al., 2015; Görg et al., 2020). The currently dominant response strategy is “eco-efficiency” or “decoupling”, i.e. the quest to reduce the use of biophysical resources or at least environmental pressures via technological solutions and efficiency gains, without questioning economic growth. Due to the scale of the current unsustainability challenge, however, large absolute reductions in resource use and emissions would be required to comply with internationally agreed upon targets, which would require “absolute decoupling” of resources and emissions from GDP at a scale and speed that has so far never been observed (Haberl et al., 2020; Wiedenhofer et al., 2020). Hence calls to move beyond eco-efficiency are increasingly voiced (Parrique et al., 2019; Hickel and Kallis, 2019; Creutzig et al., 2018). The call for sufficiency, however, is often pursued only as a moral postulate that ignores the social challenges involved (e.g. rising inequalities, the role of routines and habits, missing alternatives) and does not carefully assess the ecological implications of proposed measures (Creutzig et al., 2018).

In this paper, we have developed a different approach to investigating potentials for a social-ecological transformation of the SFS-nexus, to reduce resource use and emissions: by focusing on the political-economy and transdisciplinary dimensions of the concept of provisioning systems we propose to move the sufficiency and demand-side solutions debate towards the societal services required to support social welfare. This implies systematically assessing and comparing provisioning systems and their stock-flow-service efficiencies and outcomes. Crucially, we suggest to focus on structural societal elements of these provisioning systems, such as ownership, control, agency and power relations. For transformative insights, actors and institutions are key, which then need to be understood in relation to the technology and knowledge involved, as well as within the specific space and historical legacy as well as other temporal considerations. We strongly argue, that the role of the state needs to be scrutinized very closely. We also offer methodological approaches to systematically address the systemic interlinkages between such societal processes and the biophysical dimensions of societal resource flows and the material stocks involved,

which enable and restrict them. For sustainability transformations, we argue that we have to analyze which services can be provided by specific stocks, for whom and controlled by whom, and which resource flows are involved. Moreover, we should ask whether these resource flows are consistent with sustainability goals like the SDGs, and which alternative options are available to provide these services which less flows. In this way, the SFS-nexus can be operationalized for further research focusing on the shaping dimensions of the SFS-nexus. This is necessary, if we are to achieve doing more with less.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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